

Lithuanian case study on cybersecurity technology and information transfer

Work package	WP4 Know-how, good practice sharing, and information transfer activities
Task	T4.1. National Case Studies
Due date	28.11.2025
Submission date	28.11.2025
Deliverable lead	ULB
Version	Final
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Reviewers	WP4 partners

Abstract

Cybersecurity technology transfer and information sharing are vital for ensuring national security and resilience to cyber and hybrid threats. This report presents the results of a case study to analyse the mechanisms of cybersecurity technology transfer and information sharing in Lithuania. Furthermore, it provides recommendations for strengthening Lithuania’s national cybersecurity governance, enhancing cybersecurity technology transfer, and improving information sharing.

Keywords

Cybersecurity, cyber threats, hybrid threats, cybersecurity technology transfer, NIS 2 Directive, dual-use technologies

Document revision history

Version	Date	Description of change	Contributor(s)
VO.1	01.09.2025	Draft table of contents	Infobalt, Lithuania
VO.2	11.10.2025	Draft report, including desk research and interview results	Infobalt, Lithuania
VO.3	29.10.2025	Draft report, integrating desk research, interview, and workshop results	Infobalt, Lithuania
V1.0	06.11.2025	Draft report, integrating desk research, interview, workshop and survey results	Infobalt, Lithuania
V2.0	10.11.2025	Final version	Infobalt, Lithuania

Disclaimer

The COcyber project funded under Grant Agreement No. 101158606 is supported by the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre and funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre. Neither the European Union nor the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre can be held responsible for them.

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Project funded by the European Commission in the Digital Europe Programme

Nature of the deliverable	R
Dissemination level	
Public – fully open. e.g., website	✓
Sensitive (SEN) – limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
EU classified – RESTREINT-UE/EU-RESTRICTED, CONFIDENTIEL-UE/EU-CONFIDENTIAL, SECRET-UE/EU-SECRET under Decision 2015/444	

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence.
AMETIC	The Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Slovenia, COcyber partner leading the synergies with existing initiatives, exploitation and sustainability (WP6), and responsible for the National Case Study Report of Spain (WP4).
APT	Advanced Persistent Threat.
AUS	AUSTRALO marketing lab, COcyber partner leading communication, dissemination and stakeholder engagement (WP5).
CCDCOE	NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence.
CCIS	The Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Slovenia, COcyber partner responsible for the National Case Study Report of Slovenia (WP4).
CERT	Computer Emergency Response Team, a group of information security experts who identify, analyse and mitigate cybersecurity incidents and threats.
CRRT	Cyber Rapid Response Teams.
CSIRT	Computer Security Incident Response Team.
DEP	Digital Europe Programme, funding instrument of the European Union.
DIANA	Defence Innovation Accelerator for the North Atlantic under NATO.

DORA	Digital Operational Resilience Act – EU regulation that entered into force in January 2025 to strengthen the digital operational resilience of the financial sector.
EC	The European Commission, the European public authority funding the COcyber project.
ECC	The European Cybersecurity Competence Centre, the funding authority of the COcyber project.
ECSF	European Cybersecurity Skills Framework.
EIMIN	Ministry of the Economy and Innovation of the Republic of Lithuania.
EITD	EIT DIGITAL, COcyber coordinator leading project management (WP1) and synergies (WP6).
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity.
EOS	The European Organisation for Security, COcyber partner leading Coordination activities between cybersecurity civilian and defence spheres (WP2).
EU	The European Union (EU) is a political and economic union of 27 European countries, designed to foster economic cooperation, promote peace, and create a single market with free movement of goods, services, and people.
INFOBALT	The Digital technology sector association of Lithuania, COcyber partner responsible for the National Case Study Report of Lithuania (WP4).
ISACs	Information Sharing and Analysis Centres, non-profit organisations that provide a central resource for gathering information on cyberthreats.

IVSZ	The Information and Communication Technologies industry association of Hungary, COcyber partner responsible for the National Case Study Report of Hungary (WP4).
LC	The Lisbon Council, COcyber partner leading Cybersecurity Observatory & COcyber Platform (WP3).
LITNET	Lithuanian research and education network.
MISP	Malware Information Sharing Platform.
MoD	Ministry of National Defence.
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding.
NATO	NATO (North Atlantic Treaty Organization) is a military alliance formed in 1949, consisting of 30 member countries from Europe and North America, aimed at ensuring collective defence and security against common threats. It operates under the principle that an attack on one member is an attack on all.
NCC	National Coordination Centre under the MoD in Lithuania.
NCSC	National Cyber Security Centre.
PANG	Pennsylvania National Guard.
PESCO	Permanent Structured Cooperation.
RCDC	Regional Cyber Defence Centre under NCSC.
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise.

SOC	Security Operations Centre.
ULB	Université Libre de Bruxelles Solvay Brussels School, COcyber partner leading Know-how, good practice sharing, and information transfer activities (WP4).
WP	Work Package, form the COcyber working process.

Executive summary

Introduction

Cybersecurity technology transfer and information sharing are crucial for ensuring national security of any nation, because they enable countries to defend their critical infrastructure, ensure provision of vital services, protect sensitive data, and enhance collective defence against threats, which are continuously increasing in number and sophistication. Sharing intelligence on cyber threats and vulnerabilities enables rapid, coordinated responses, prevents attacks from spreading, and enhances public-private partnerships essential for comprehensive national defence.

Furthermore, due to current geopolitical situation, Lithuania together with other Baltic and Nordic countries is experiencing constant pressure and increasing volume of cyber and hybrid attacks from hostile neighbouring countries. This report provides a comprehensive overview of Lithuania's cybersecurity landscape and proposes recommendations for strengthening Lithuania's national cybersecurity governance, enhancing cybersecurity technology transfer, and improving information sharing.

Objective

The purpose of this document is to present the design, execution, and results of the case study, performed in Lithuania during May – November 2025. The aim of the case study was to analyse and enhance the mechanisms of cybersecurity technology transfer and information sharing within Lithuania.

Methodology

A unified methodological framework was designed and implemented in performing four national case studies to investigate cybersecurity technology transfer and information-sharing mechanisms within Spain, Lithuania, Slovenia, and Hungary. A mixed-methods

approach was adopted to ensure a comprehensive understanding of each country's cybersecurity landscape, facilitating both depth and breadth in data collection and analysis.

Four methods have been applied in each case study:

1. Desk research, which included an extensive review of national cybersecurity strategies, policies, legal frameworks, and academic literature to establish a foundational understanding of each country's cybersecurity environment.
2. Semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders representing government agencies, private sector entities, academic institutions, civil society organisations, and military-related organisations were carried out to gather in-depth qualitative insights.
3. Online survey was disseminated to a broader group of stakeholders in each country to collect quantitative data and validate findings from the interviews and desk research.
4. National validation workshops with cybersecurity experts were performed in each country at the end of the case studies to review preliminary findings, ensuring the accuracy and relevance of the data and interpretations.

Results

Stakeholders representing the following five types of organizations have participated in the case study in Lithuania: government agencies and regulators; private sector representatives (including critical infrastructure operators); research and academic institutions; civil society or industry associations; military-related organisations.

10 stakeholders have participated in interviews, 28 – in survey, and 17 in the national validation workshop. All the data was analysed, integrated, and presented in this report.

After analysing the results of case study, the following suggestions (needs) have been derived for strengthening Lithuania's national cybersecurity governance, enhancing

technology transfer mechanisms, improving information sharing practices, and managing dual-use technologies:

- There is a need to operationalize the enforcement the Cybersecurity Law to ensure that all cybersecurity entities comply with it, especially with regards to information sharing.
- There is a need of cybersecurity policies and guidelines for all organizations in the country, not only identified cybersecurity entities, which are covered by the Cybersecurity Law.
- Due to the current geopolitical situation in Lithuania and the region, more attention needs to be given to hybrid threats. Thus, there is a need for an appropriate “hybrid” approach to defend against hybrid threats.
- Consistent rules for all participants and a clear certification process required for transferring cybersecurity technologies need to be defined.
- Lack of trust is the main obstacle for cybersecurity information sharing. Thus, there is an urgent need for developing and implementing novel approaches to increase trust among organizations for timely information sharing.
- To enhance international collaboration and information sharing, there is a need to have a unified framework which would be acceptable in all countries.
- There is a need to perform policy review and regulatory impact analysis on dual-use technologies and propose guidance to aid developers with dual-use technology transfer.
- Education system needs to be revised to include cybersecurity education from the young age (primary schools) up to university level and beyond (life-long-learning).
- Public awareness is still low, while general population is continuously getting more vulnerable to cyberattacks. New effective ways to educate people of different age groups are urgently needed.
- Lack of cybersecurity skills is extreme and needs to be addressed at the national level.

1. Introduction

This section introduces the purpose and scope of the case study, providing context on the importance of cybersecurity technology and information transfer in the national landscape. It outlines the rationale for conducting the study, the key questions it seeks to address, and the methodologies used to gather and analyse data.

1.1 Background and context of cybersecurity technology and information transfer

Cybersecurity has become a cornerstone of national security and economic stability. As digital infrastructures expand, the need for robust cybersecurity measures and effective information sharing becomes paramount.

Technology transfer in cybersecurity refers to the process of moving cybersecurity technologies from research and development into practical applications, enhancing national capabilities to prevent, detect, and respond to cyber threats.

International collaboration plays a critical role in strengthening cybersecurity. Sharing information about threats, vulnerabilities, and best practices across borders helps build a collective defence against cyber adversaries. At the national level, coordinated efforts among government agencies, private sector entities, and academic institutions are essential for developing and implementing effective cybersecurity strategies.

In Lithuania, cybersecurity technology transfer plays an important role in strengthening national security as part of development of the Lithuanian defence industry. It allows advanced research outcomes and innovative solutions developed by science and business communities to be channelled directly into addressing defence and critical infrastructure challenges. This strengthens our ability to prevent, detect, and respond to emerging cyber threats.

Lithuania is no different from other EU member states that are stepping up their defence policies and, at the same time, their defence spending. Every year there are more and more companies in the country getting involved in the defence industry, more attention from foreign investors, more demand for production, and ultimately more demand for new defence technologies, including cybersecurity, new systems, and non-standard solutions.

In 2024, a tripartite agreement (MoU) has been signed by representatives of the Innovation Agency, the Lithuanian Armed Forces, and the Defence Resources Agency. The MoU serves as a basis for advancing defence technology, creating conditions for the growth of industry in this field, and strengthening national capabilities. The memorandum states that the institutions will cooperate in implementing measures and projects that will enable the Lithuanian defence industry to create high value-added products. A close coordination between civilian and military structures is required for efficient state-level threat response. The civilian sector plays a critical role in it, especially in supplying the resources for the Armed Forces.

One of the most notable events of 2025 was the launch of the Vytis program, aimed at establishing Lithuania as a regional defence and cybersecurity industry hub. This is the first initiative of its kind focussed on strengthening the defence sector and developing new technologies that can later be applied in other sectors. Its measures include the Defence Innovation Vouchers program, which has already allocated €1 million, and invitations to use the Miltech Sandbox infrastructure for technology testing and prototyping. Participation in international events such as Baltic Miltech Summit conference and cooperation with global companies also motivate Lithuanian cybersecurity ecosystem to remain competitive and recognised at the European and transatlantic level.

As for cybersecurity in the civilian sector, the development of the Regional Cyber Defence Centre (RCDC) under the National Cyber Security Centre (NCSC) under the Ministry of National Defence (MoD) is another successful initiative. RCDC's mission is to perform cyber threat analysis, organize trainings, and promote collaboration with strategic

partners. There are plans to further develop cyber threat intelligence exchange, scientific research in cybersecurity, and cyber threat hunt operations in the Centre.

Advancement in technology development has both strengthened and weakened cybersecurity of the systems. E.g., Cloud services enabled the flexibility in sharing data not only within organizations and their partners, but also made information sharing more resilient against various cyberattacks. Also, Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools enable the analysis of large quantities of data and help in detect anomalies and cyberattacks.

However, most of technologies could be used by malicious actors to cause harm to the systems and the society as well. Thus, this must be taken into consideration when developing new technologies. One of such technologies is Quantum computing, which could disrupt existing cryptographic systems used for cybersecurity. Organizations, especially those representing critical infrastructure sectors, could be affected if quantum technologies become a reality. The use of AI by attackers is even more urgent concern, which must be addressed. Attackers are starting to apply AI for variety of offensive activities, such as discovery of system vulnerabilities, malware creation, or social engineering.

Information sharing is crucial because it facilitates collective defence against sophisticated threats. In Lithuania, both formal and informal information sharing mechanisms are well established. However, in practice, there is still some reluctance to disclose vulnerability and incident data due to lack of trust and possible negative consequences, such as reputational damage or financial losses.

1.2 Objectives of the case study

The primary objective of this case study is to analyse and enhance the mechanisms of cybersecurity technology transfer and information sharing within Lithuania, contributing to the broader goals of the CoCyber project.

The specific objectives of Lithuania's case study are:

- Identify and document current national frameworks, policies, and practices related to cybersecurity technology transfer and information sharing.
- Identify key stakeholders across government, industry, academia, civil society, and the military sphere, involved in cybersecurity initiatives.
- Evaluate the effectiveness of existing mechanisms for technology transfer and information sharing, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement.
- Analyse challenges and barriers hindering effective cybersecurity collaboration and propose solutions to overcome them.
- Formulate actionable policy recommendations to enhance national cybersecurity resilience through improved technology transfer and information sharing.

1.3 Scope and limitations

This case study focuses on the national mechanisms for cybersecurity technology transfer and information sharing, examining the roles of various stakeholders, including government bodies, private sector organisations, and academic institutions. The study encompasses policies, frameworks, and practices currently in place, as well as recent initiatives aimed at enhancing these processes.

Some limitations of this case study are:

- The study is confined to publicly available information and data obtained through stakeholder interviews and surveys.
- It does not delve into classified or sensitive information that is not accessible through open sources.
- The findings are based on the current state of affairs and may not account for rapidly evolving cybersecurity threats or technologies.

2. Methodology

The national case studies adopt a mixed-method approach combining desk research, semi-structured interviews, an online survey, and a national expert validation workshop. This approach ensures comprehensive evidence collection and validation across Spain, Lithuania, Slovenia, and Hungary.

2.1 Research methods

This section outlines the methodological framework employed in the COcyber national case studies to investigate cybersecurity technology transfer and information-sharing mechanisms within Spain, Lithuania, Slovenia, and Hungary. A mixed-methods approach was adopted to ensure a comprehensive understanding of each country's cybersecurity landscape, facilitating both depth and breadth in data collection and analysis.

The research design encompasses four key components:

- Desk research: An extensive review of national cybersecurity strategies, policies, legal frameworks, and academic literature was conducted to establish a foundational understanding of each country's cybersecurity environment.
- Semi-structured interviews: Targeted interviews with key stakeholders—including representatives from government agencies, private sector entities, academic institutions, and civil society organisations—were carried out to gather in-depth qualitative insights.
- Online survey: A structured survey was disseminated to a broader group of stakeholders to collect quantitative data and validate findings from the interviews and desk research.
- National validation workshops: Each country hosted a workshop with at least 15 experts to review preliminary findings, ensuring the accuracy and relevance of the data and interpretations.

This multi-faceted methodology was designed to capture a holistic view of cybersecurity practices and challenges in each nation, providing a robust basis for comparative analysis and policy recommendations.

2.1.1. Desk research

A preliminary literature review and policy analysis has been conducted at the national level. This phase includes the review of:

- National cybersecurity strategies and policies
- Legal and regulatory frameworks
- Existing technology transfer and information-sharing mechanisms
- Relevant academic and industry publications

2.1.2. Semi-structured stakeholder interviews

Using a common interview guide, a series of in-depth interviews will be carried out with national stakeholders.

Stakeholder categories included:

- Government agencies and regulators;
- Private sector representatives (including critical infrastructure operators);
- Research and academic institutions;
- Civil society or industry associations;
- Military-related organisations.

In total, 10 interviews have been conducted and two stakeholders per category have been interviewed. A detailed list of stakeholders is provided in Annex 4.

2.1.3. Online stakeholder survey

An online survey has been distributed to a broader set of mapped stakeholders in each country. This survey aimed to:

- Reach a wider audience beyond direct interviews;
- Validate preliminary findings;

- Collect additional quantitative or qualitative insights.

Lithuania has received 28 survey responses: 14 participants represented private sector (50%), 6 – academic/research institutions (21.5%), another 6 – military related organizations (21.5%), and 2 – public/government organizations (7%).

2.1.4. National experts' validation workshop

A national validation workshop is organised in each country in October 2025, gathering at least 10 national experts.

The objectives are:

- To present and validate the draft findings
- To gather final inputs and ensure stakeholder alignment
- To refine recommendations based on multi-sectoral expert feedback

In Lithuania, the workshop took place on 22nd October, where 17 national cybersecurity experts have participated. A draft of the report has been provided to participants one week before the workshop so that they had enough time to familiarize with the initial case study findings and prepare for the discussion.

2.2 Data analysis and reporting

Data gathered through desk research, interviews, and the online survey has been analysed thematically and synthesised into draft case study reports. The findings have been validated through the national workshops before finalising the deliverables.

3. National cybersecurity landscape

This section examines the Lithuania's existing cybersecurity framework, policies, and key stakeholders. It identifies the legal and regulatory landscape, as well as the institutions

responsible for overseeing cybersecurity efforts. It also analyses national cybersecurity challenges, strengths, and areas for improvement.

3.1 Overview of national cybersecurity policies and strategies

In Lithuania, the Law on Cybersecurity came into effect in 2014 (Republic of Lithuania, 2014). It established a framework for cybersecurity system in Lithuania, defining organization, management and control of the system, as well as terms and definitions. In 2018, the National Cybersecurity Strategy has been approved by the Government of the Republic of Lithuania (Republic of Lithuania, 2018). It defined the most important pillars of the national cybersecurity policy. The following five targets have been identified by the strategy:

- (1) To strengthen cybersecurity of the country and the development of cyber defence capabilities.
- (2) To ensure prevention and investigation of criminal offences in cyber space.
- (3) To promote cybersecurity culture and development of innovation.
- (4) To strengthen a close cooperation between private and public sectors.
- (5) To enhance international cooperation and ensure the fulfilment of international obligations in the field of cybersecurity.

On 20th September 2023, the National Cyber Security Development Programme until 2030 was approved by the Government of the Republic of Lithuania through Resolution No. 746. As a continuation of the initial National Cybersecurity Strategy, it aims to ensure the cyber resilience of the State and the development of cybersecurity capabilities.

The programme is accompanied by the Action Plan of the National Cybersecurity Development Programme, approved by Order No. V-98 of the Minister of National Defence of the Republic of Lithuania on the 5th February 2024. The implementers of the Action Plan are public institutions: the Ministry of National Defence, National Cyber Security Center

under the Ministry of National Defence, the State Telecommunications Center and Police Department under the Ministry of the Interior.

The main activities related to the implementation of the Programme are focused on the renewal of cybersecurity model, the creation of a national SOC/CSIRT modular system, the strengthening of cybersecurity skills and competencies, as well as the enhancement of cybercrime investigation capacities. The implementation of these activities is foreseen up to the first quarter of 2026. According to MoD, all the activities are progressing smoothly and are in line with the approved Action Plan so far.

On October 18th, 2024, the updated Cybersecurity Law entered into force. It implements the following European Union legal acts:

- NIS 2 Directive (EU Dir 2022/2555, 2022);
- Cybersecurity Act (EU Reg 2019/881, 2019);
- Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing the European Cybersecurity Industrial, Technology and Research Competence Centre and the Network of National Coordination Centres (EU Reg 2021/887, 2021).

The provisions of the NIS 2 Directive transposed into the Cybersecurity Law are aimed at strengthening the cybersecurity governance model in Lithuania. The law and other related implementing legal acts are expected to provide clear guidelines for cybersecurity entities on various aspects such as cybersecurity risk analysis and management, cybersecurity incident management and reporting, implementation of technical cybersecurity measures, etc.

Countering cyber threats in Lithuania is based on three pillars:

1. Firstly, we are strengthening our Armed Forces by newly established LT Cyber Command (2025) and building cyber conscription for national defence.
2. Secondly, we are increasing cyber resilience in society and critical infrastructure. We are strengthening the NCSC, defining its strategic directions and implementing

structural reforms. This will be critical in supporting our Armed Forces with all services (fuel, electricity, water, etc.).

3. Thirdly, we are amplifying collective cyber defence by training with our Allies and the like-minded partners.

Interview results revealed that most of participants were satisfied with the national cybersecurity strategy. They believe that it is quite effective, and that Lithuania is in a good position compared to other countries. Strategy enabled successful cybersecurity community building and private-public sector partnerships. In addition, the results of implementing the strategy are good: most of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), defined in the strategy, have been achieved.

As for the Cybersecurity Law, adopted in 2024, its effectiveness still needs to be seen. So far, over 1400 cybersecurity entities have been identified, which must comply with this law. In the near future, this number will increase to include supply chain organizations as well. The obligations for these organizations have been clearly identified by the law. However, some interviewees and workshop participants believe, that to ensure the compliance with the law, fines will need to be introduced: *"companies are afraid of fines; only when we start implementing the fines, companies will start acting immediately"*.

However, according to some Interview participants, the national cybersecurity strategy is a little too broad and the technical aspects are left not covered. The NCSC provides organizations with the cybersecurity frameworks based on principles, standards, and best practices, but lacks technical guidance.

More than half of the survey participants (55%) agree that the national cybersecurity strategy is effective, while 19% believe that its highly effective. However, some participants raised concerns that although legislation and policies are in place, the practical implementation (for example controlling body) is understaffed and enforcement of implementation is not monitored, thus actual progress is very slow. Also, the next steps are not completely clear.

It is important to note that the aim of Cybersecurity Law and, consequently, of the NCSC who is responsible for implementing it, is to increase the overall level of cybersecurity and resilience of all core critical sectors in Lithuania, including energy, transportation, communications, water, finance, and healthcare sectors. Currently, some of the sectors, such as, e.g., financial, are more advanced and they follow sector-specific regulations, such as Digital Operational Resilience Act (DORA), while other sectors are lagging behind. NCSC is determined to provide all the necessary support to all sectors to achieve a high cybersecurity level in line with the National Cyber Security Development Programme.

3.1 Main stakeholders in the country

The organizational structure of the Lithuanian cybersecurity ecosystem is defined in the Cybersecurity Law:

- Cybersecurity policy in Lithuania is formulated by the Ministry of National Defence (MoD).
- The Ministry of Foreign Affairs participates in the formulation of cybersecurity policy to the extent necessary to establish the legal regulation of the application of diplomatic measures in response to cyber threats and cyber incidents.
- The National Cyber Security Centre under MoD (NCSC) also participates in the formulation of cybersecurity policy to the extent necessary to establish the legal regulation of the activities and supervision of cybersecurity entities in order to perform the functions assigned to it by law.

MoD shapes national cybersecurity policy and works to ensure resilience against evolving threats. Its priorities include strengthening cyber incident and risk management, enhancing the maturity of organisations, and ensuring the security of critical supply chains. This priority is implemented through the requirement to strengthen cybersecurity in organizations that carry out significant activities in the country. Meanwhile, the existing National Cybersecurity Development Program supports organizations in implementing these requirements, directing a large part of the funds for training, strengthening cyber incident management, and implementing individual cybersecurity needs.

Regarding cybersecurity policy implementation, it is performed by the NCSC, the Lithuanian police and the State Data Protection Inspectorate. In addition, the NCSC, in coordination with the National Crisis Management Centre, notifies European Union institutions of crises related to cyber incidents that the Republic of Lithuania is unable to manage on its own.

There is also the cybersecurity policy and implementation advisory body – Cybersecurity Council. Furthermore, the newly established (in 2025) Cyber Defence Command of the Lithuanian Armed Forces deals with all the military-related cyber issues. They are preparing for the worst-case scenario to fight a war in the cyber domain.

The Ministry of National Defence, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the NCSC, the Lithuanian Police, and the State Data Protection Inspectorate cooperate with each other and with other state institutions, including the Communications Regulatory Authority, other competent authorities in accordance with Regulation (EU) No. 910/2014 on electronic identification and trust services for electronic transactions (EU Reg 910/2014, 2014) and Regulation (EU) 2022/2554 on the resilience of digital operations in the financial sector (EU Reg 2022/2554, 2022), as well as with the National Crisis Management Centre, including the exchange of information on incidents, cyber threats, and near-miss incidents.

The competent authorities of EU Member States (like NCSC in Lithuania) also cooperate with each other to assist each other in managing cybersecurity risks and incidents, and to share experience and information. To this end, upon receiving a reasoned request for mutual assistance from the competent authority of another Member State, the NCSC has the duty and the right to carry out the inspection of cybersecurity entities and/or enforcement measures provided for by law.

In the academic field, we have the Lithuanian research and education network (LITNET). It is aimed at protecting all educational institutions like schools, universities, libraries, laboratories, etc. from cyber threats.

In addition, we have good practices of collaboration with the private sector, especially with the critical infrastructure companies related to the IT services and telecommunications. They can support and help the governmental entities to fight against threats. NCSC closely collaborates with the Lithuanian DigiTech Sector Association INFOBALT and the Association of Cybersecurity Experts.

Furthermore, some big companies such as Tesonet, are developing cybersecurity technologies and supporting other organizations and public institutions technologically and with human resources. E.g., company Oxylabs, owned by Tesonet, developed a real-time tracking tool, which is capable to detect child pornography content. This tool is being used not only by the Lithuanian police department, but also by police departments in Belgium, Netherlands, France, and Germany.

In summary, there are numerous organizations working in cybersecurity sector in Lithuania, as shown in Figure 1 (Benetis, 2025). They are grouped in the following four areas:

- (1) Technology Developers, Resellers, Integrators, Consultancy;
- (2) Distributors;
- (3) Educators, Research, Communities;
- (4) National Capabilities.

As of September 2025, there were 179 organizations in total: 120 in group (1), 14 in group (2), 33 in group (3), and 12 in group (4).

According to interviewees, comparing to other countries, Lithuania is in a good position, since it has a centralised approach to cybersecurity. We have one single ministry responsible for cybersecurity – MoD, which has all subordinate organizations, capable of ensuring cybersecurity. So, if we want to protect our nation from cyber threats, we are required to do a lot of coordination among different governmental and public organizations. But when all stakeholders are under one supervision, it is very easy to do that. There are almost no barriers because information does not transcend ministerial

boundaries. Otherwise, it would require engaging in bilateral, trilateral agreements and process would be lengthy.

Figure 1. Cybersecurity@Lithuania Map. Version 2025-09-03. © Vilius Benetis.

<https://github.com/vibenas/Cybersecurity-Lithuania-Map>

Current settings create a very good environment for everybody to share information and to react very quickly. E.g., in other countries cyber-related functions are dispersed through different ministries, thus creating very huge challenges for both civilian and military organizations in cyber information exchange. For instance, as for military to be ready to fight in cyberspace during wartime, it needs to train in peacetime. But the legislation does not allow that because we are in peacetime, including cyberspace. From one perspective, civilian authority understands the necessity, but legislation hinders military from taking any actions in cyberspace. However, Lithuania is in a good position in this regard.

3.2 National cybersecurity challenges and gaps

Cybersecurity challenges in Lithuania reflect both global and national trends. They can be grouped into several categories, as described below.

Emergent technologies related challenges

At the European level, MoD makes efforts to address emerging risks such as quantum computing, which threatens encryption, through coordinated EU-wide actions and solutions. It also must focus on the dual role of AI – as both a tool for strengthening cybersecurity and a potential source of new risks. Efforts are also made to manage the risks posed by digital products with cybersecurity and AI elements and to further strengthen the response to cyber incidents and potential cybersecurity crises.

Rapid technology development is a huge challenge. Due to the use of AI tools, the learning curve to conduct various cyberattacks and malicious activities is not as high as it was before. Defenders can also use AI tools for analysing data and traffic, but attackers always have an advantage, as they need to find only few vulnerabilities to conduct cyberattacks, and defenders need to protect everything.

Challenges caused by geopolitical situation

It should be noted that cybersecurity in the Baltic States is exceptional due to their geopolitical situation and constant pressure from hostile neighbouring countries. The region is constantly facing cyberattacks from unfriendly neighbouring countries. In the near future, state-sponsored actors could become a big challenge at the national level. They have resources and capabilities to have an impact to any nation.

Cyberspace is widespread; therefore, all state critical sectors are in it. Moreover, most sectors are creating an economic power for a nation. Each attack, which is well organized, might significantly diminish the capacity of a nation to sustain its economy. That's why, the next challenge for any nation is to be prepared to protect its cyberspace from the state-sponsored actors, especially those who have huge resources and interest to harm particular nation. In contrast to cybercriminals who are looking for making some profit, state-sponsored actors seek to weaken a state or in some circumstances destroy it.

Hybrid threats

Hybrid threats are the coordinated harmful activities aimed at undermining a state or an institution, using a variety of means, often combined. These means may include cyberattacks or physical actions, information manipulation, economic influence, military threats, etc. (European Council, 2025).

Lithuania faces a high risk of hybrid threats from Belarus due to close relationship between Belarus and Russia. Belarusian actors have been involved in cyberattacks that align with Russian geopolitical interests, especially against neighbouring countries and NATO members, such as Lithuania. This collaboration often involves coordinated cyber espionage, disinformation campaigns, and attacks on critical infrastructure, reflecting a shared strategy to exert influence and cause disruption of vital functions (Stitilis et al, 2024). E.g., recently, Lithuania had to temporarily close two airports due to a hybrid attacks from Belarus, when dozens of contraband-filled air balloons entered Lithuania's air space. This also prompted Lithuania to shut border crossing with Belarus (France 24, 2025).

Limited resources and insufficient funding

Lack of resources and shortage of dedicated funding for cybersecurity is a big challenge that small states, such as Lithuania, are facing. Insufficient funding has been identified as one of the significant challenges by 57% of survey participants.

In Lithuania, most of organizations are Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). In SMEs, due to limited resources, IT systems are often created and maintained by multiple organizations and individuals, each trying to protect their own systems, while malicious actors are well-funded and highly focussed (Juozapavicius et al., 2025).

Furthermore, it is challenging for SMEs to have essential cybersecurity staff. The European Cybersecurity Skills Framework (ECSF), published by ENISA in 2022, defines 12 cybersecurity roles each organization should have, including Chief Information Security Officer (CISO), cyber incident responder, cyber threat intelligence specialist, cybersecurity architect, and penetration tester among others (ENISA, 2022). However, in Lithuania, the majority of businesses have less than 50 employees, where cybersecurity

professionals are expected to cover multiple roles, reducing their effectiveness and capabilities (Juozapavicius, 2025).

Legacy systems' challenges

Legacy systems pose significant cybersecurity challenges to critical infrastructure in the Baltic Sea region, including Lithuania, due to outdated technologies, unsupported software, and unsupported hardware that lack modern security features. These systems are common due to high costs, complexity, and the difficulty of switching to newer technologies without affecting operations (RCDC, 2024).

Lack of skilled cybersecurity professionals

Shortage of cybersecurity skills is another major challenge not only in Lithuania, but worldwide. As stated by interview participants, cybersecurity is quite a new area, and we simply do not have enough people who would be able to work in cybersecurity field, which makes it difficult to develop new programmes, to increase resilience and so on. In particular, it is important to have experienced specialists, who would drive the development. That's why it is very important to turn our focus from technology development to skills development.

This has been confirmed by survey results: lack of skills has been identified as the most significant cybersecurity challenge by 82% of participants.

The lack of cybersecurity professionals is particularly acute in public sector, including national infrastructure organizations, due to higher salaries in the private sector. According to Bukauskas et al., 2022, the salaries in public sector are 15–50% lower. This leaves public sector less protected from cyberattacks. NCSC is aware of this situation and is giving free courses to citizens to reduce the lack of competences and raise the awareness.

Lack of public awareness

At society level, people' understanding about cybersecurity threats is not sufficient. In Lithuania, we are dealing with disinformation, fake news, and social engineering threats

already, and their amount could increase due to geopolitical situation. Thus, it is crucial to increase public awareness. Furthermore, at organization level, there is a lack of cyber culture and cyber hygiene. According to interviewees, awareness and cyber culture cannot be based only on voluntary training. Training must become obligatory, and the skills need to be continuously tested.

Social engineering remains the main reason for cybersecurity incidents. According to MoD report on the overview of cybersecurity status in Lithuania, 59% of all incidents recorded in 2024 were caused by social engineering, where criminals manipulate people to obtain login details or other sensitive information (MoD, 2025a).

Multiple interview participants emphasized that social engineering is biggest challenge for Lithuania in the cybersecurity area, especially in the field of finance. It includes frauds with the crypto investment activities, payments, charity activities and other things – these are the classic fraud schemes that use cyber-space for their purposes.

Limited public awareness has also been mentioned by 61% of survey participants as one of the cybersecurity challenges in Lithuania.

Insufficient cybersecurity education

Cybersecurity education is still not sufficient in Lithuania. Education programmes need to be revised to include cybersecurity teaching and training courses for all and at all levels: from primary schools up to post-graduate education. Everyone must have an understanding of cybersecurity, not only computer science students. Thus, study programmes at schools and universities must be revised in a harmonized way to include cybersecurity education. Furthermore, cybersecurity skills programmes for training professionals from other fields should be developed at a national level to address the skills shortage. According to experts, who participated in interviews and workshop, new university graduates from informatics programmes with specialization in cybersecurity are simply not sufficient to address the needs of the country.

Legal and jurisdictional challenges

There are numerous jurisdictional challenges. Due to the Internet's borderless nature, we face conflicting national laws and difficulties in enforcing them across different countries. Key difficulties include determining which country's laws to apply, attributing attacks to specific actors, and the lack of international cooperation and legal harmonization required for investigation and prosecution.

There are some legal challenges as well, e.g., related to the implementation of responsible disclosure doctrine. In 2021, the amendments to the Cybersecurity Law have been made, aimed at legalizing the vulnerability disclosure model in Lithuania. According to interview participants, its implementation is still a huge challenge for the prosecutors, police officers and the courts. For several year when we have a responsible disclosure doctrine, we do not have successful examples of its application yet.

Limited coverage of organizations by the Cybersecurity Law

According to the Official Statistics Portal, as of 1st January 2024, there were 142,954 enterprises in operation in Lithuania, 119,944 of them were SMEs (Official Statistics Portal, 2025). However, currently the national cybersecurity law covers only critical entities, which amount to around 1,500 – only 1% of all enterprises. The rest of organizations should implement cybersecurity measures as well, but it is not required by law and will depend on their awareness, motivation, and available resources.

3.3 International cooperation and partnerships in cybersecurity

In Lithuania, we have the Regional Cyber Defence Centre, RCDC, under the NCSC. Its objectives include strengthening cooperation with the United States of America, Ukraine, Sakartvelo and other strategic partners of Lithuania in the field of cybersecurity. The list of partners is continuously expanding. Currently, it is focussed on specific regions, such as the Baltic countries, Nordic countries, and Asia-Pacific countries. The Centre carries out cyber threat analysis and cyber threat hunting jointly with the partners and conducts international scientific software/hardware research in the area of cybersecurity. In addition, Lithuania actively participates and cooperates on several multilateral formats

such as the US-led Counter Ransomware Initiative (CRI) and a NATO flagship project Cyber Champions Summit. Military organizations engage in cooperation with NATO organization and nations. Cyber-related cooperation is well established; there are different initiatives (classified).

On the EU cyber defence side, Lithuania leads Permanent Structured Cooperation (PESCO) Cyber Rapid Response Teams (CRRT) capability. It has become fully operational and is composed of civil-military (civ-mil) cyber experts from 12 participating EU Member States. The benefits are visibility in the international arena and mutual assistance in countering cyber threats. For instance, one of the PESCO CRRT deployments was to conduct cyber threat hunting operation during the 2024 European Parliament elections in Lithuania.

MoD has been pursuing an extensive and ambitious cooperation programme with the Pennsylvania National Guard (PANG) for three decades as well. PANG contributes to Lithuanian-hosted and U.S.-hosted cybersecurity exercises, participates in conducting analysis of cyber threats facing the region, and cooperates closely with the NCSC.

Furthermore, Lithuania actively collaborates with Australia in the field of hybrid threats, in particular, disinformation and the fake elements. In 2022, Mykolas Romeris University (MRU) in Lithuania, together with the Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology (RMIT) in Australia, established the Australian-Lithuanian Cyber Research Network (ALCRN), and in 2023 – the Australian-Lithuanian Hybrid Threats Centre, which is dedicated to identifying and responding to ever-evolving hybrid threats.

In addition, Lithuania participates in international cybersecurity cooperation through joint exercises, knowledge sharing with partners, and collaborative development of best practices. These partnerships provide knowledge exchange and access to broader expertise; however, challenges remain in integrating and applying shared knowledge effectively at the national level.

Another example of successful international collaboration are the cyber courses in collaboration with the Try Hack Me platform, created by a Lithuanian research institution in partnership with the US-based cyber company Coding Dojo by Colorado University. This partnership enabled a launch of cyber training provided by Lithuanian organization, recognized in Germany and worldwide.

According to interview participants, the most tangible benefit of international collaboration is an increased situation awareness. If something happens in one nation, probably in the near future it will happen in another nation. By sharing information, we can understand what is happening in cyberspace and can plan our actions accordingly. This increases our capability detect cyber-attacks and to sense situation in the cyberspace. Another benefit is “know-how”. Sometimes we do not know how to solve a problem. However, if another nation has found a solution, it can share it with others. Also, sharing international best practices helps all communicating parties implement good practices faster.

There are sector-specific international collaboration initiatives. It is common for critical infrastructure organizations to collaborate with their partners in other countries. E.g., organizations in energy sector operate in European environment exchanging electricity, thus they closely collaborate with organizations in Latvia, Estonia, Poland, Nordic and other countries, including US. The main benefits threat intelligence sharing, experience sharing, incident response sharing to avoid similar situations at other sites.

There is international collaboration at the university level as well. Universities participate in various international projects in cybersecurity area we collaborate with partners in other countries by performing joint research, sharing information, best practices, use cases, which helps to increase cybersecurity level in universities, to pass it to students and to the society.

A big challenge for international collaboration is the difference in legal frameworks between countries. We don't have one unified framework which would be acceptable for each country. Each country can interpret some aspects of the regulations in their own

way. Another challenge is the reluctance to share the information. Not all nations want to share information, because they understand that as soon as information has been released, nation loses control of it. There is no possibility to know how information is used inside a nation and who would get access to it.

Survey results showed that international collaboration was extremely important for 52% of participants' organizations, and moderately/highly important for 48%. Furthermore, 89% of participants believe that international collaboration enhances Lithuania's cybersecurity capabilities.

4. Technology transfer framework

This section explores the mechanisms through which cybersecurity technologies are transferred within and between different sectors, including civilian and defence industries. It assesses existing technology transfer policies, identifies best practices, and highlights challenges faced in facilitating smooth transfers of innovation.

4.1. Definition and importance of technology transfer in cybersecurity

In the context of cybersecurity, technology transfer is understood as the process of moving research results, innovative solutions, and advanced technologies developed in academia and industry into practical applications that strengthen national defence and cyber resilience. For the MoD, this implies ensuring that cutting-edge cybersecurity tools are effectively adapted to the needs of our Armed Forces and critical infrastructure in Lithuania.

Through initiatives such as the trilateral memorandum on defence innovations, MoD together with other responsible state institutions foster cooperation between state institutions, the Innovation Agency, academia, and private companies. This accelerates the integration of cutting-edge technologies into both defence and civilian sectors, enhancing resilience not only for Lithuania but also for the wider European and NATO security ecosystem.

For military organizations, cybersecurity technology transfer is very important. Military in Lithuania does not have capacity to create innovative technologies and relies on the commercial sector. In NATO, the Defence Innovation Accelerator for the North Atlantic (DIANA) deals with all initiatives regarding innovation. During a recent meeting DIANA informed conference attendees that it had assigned huge amount of funds for start-ups. Since development of certain technologies (e.g., quantum, blockchain, AI) requires significant technical expertise and financial resources, DIANA wants to support them as sophisticated, emerging and disruptive technologies are crucial for NATO to transform its ways of conducting military operations in the future by employing benefits of digital transformation.

NCSC is not directly involved in technology transfer. It is looking for technologies already available in the market that could be used for specific purposes. However, it has an ambition to create a Cyber Campus in Lithuania by the end of 2027. It is a collaboration project between NCSC, other state institutions, businesses and academia. It would operate under the same roof and to look for greater cooperation in innovation area, but right now it is only a project. Already, there are some examples of good practices in France, Israel, Sweden on how such campuses work.

Lithuanian universities are not actively involved in the cybersecurity technology transfer yet, due to rapid changes in this area. Currently, universities are mostly involved in cybersecurity research and knowledge transfer to study programmes, students, and the society.

According to interview participants, in Lithuania universities work at a slower speed as compared to businesses, thus for university to create a new product in this area is very challenging. However, at the same time, cybersecurity technology transfer is crucial for ensuring rapid uptake of innovations from research labs to operational environments, making practical tools available for use as soon as they are developed.

Thus, this situation could change due to increased use of AI and potential use of quantum technologies by malicious actors. This will require close collaboration with universities

performing research in AI and quantum computing area in development of novel cybersecurity solutions.

Survey participants agree that technology transfer was important advancing cybersecurity capabilities in Lithuania: 44% defined it as important, while 41% – as extremely important.

Some interview participants believe that we don't need to invest in technology that much. We need to invest more in quality, instead of having many tools and having to replace them frequently. Most of the technology created 5 years ago we are not using any more, while some of the technologies that we need to protect are still too outdated. So, it is more crucial to invest in people. Because people need to know what to do with the technology: *"you could have a fantastic solution in your hands, but you will not know what to do with it; then it's zero value; we have created a lot of technology already, so maybe we need to make a better order with it and to use it better."*

4.2. Legal and regulatory framework governing technology transfer

Lithuania's legal and regulatory environment overall supports cybersecurity technology development but is not fully optimized for rapid innovation. Strict procurement laws and dual-use export regulations can hinder integration of research outputs. Recent initiatives like the MitreEN Sandbox have expedited some processes and improved collaboration among government, academia, and industry.

In defence sector, the Law on Defence and Security Industry defines who in the state is responsible for development, innovation, procurement, and industrial cooperation in this area (MoD, 2025b). It mandates local industrial involvement and requires the foreign suppliers to partner with Lithuanian companies for joint projects, licensing, and manufacturing.

This law is truly unique, because only in few countries in the world where the defence industry is regulated by law. It is worth mentioning that Defense and Security Industry Law has also led to the establishment of a new Defense Industry Policy and Innovation Department within the Defense Resources Agency. The activities of the Defense Industry Policy and Innovation Department are focused on finding and implementing innovative solutions, as well as developing the capabilities of the Lithuanian Armed Forces, which is necessary in view of the changing security challenges in the region. In addition to this, the department provides a platform for product testing.

4.3. National institutions responsible for facilitating technology transfer

The main organizations responsible for technology transfer are Innovation Agency, Ministry of Economy and Innovation, and the defence system organizations: MoD, Lithuanian Armed Forces, the Defence Resources Agency, the National Coordination Center (NCC), whose tasks in Lithuania are performed by the National Cyber Security Center.

The GovTech Lab Lithuania under the Innovation Agency are actively working in helping the companies, especially the small companies with technology transfer, including cybersecurity technologies. They are organising different events and trying to engage companies inside and outside Lithuania and attract investment. They have a clear purpose – to help companies create real working technologies.

Furthermore, Infobalt, universities, and commercial institutions and companies are involved in the technology transfer in Lithuania.

The Riftenem Union Lizdeika company and the MitreEN Sandbox are examples of the national institutions actively involved in cybersecurity technology transfer, facilitating collaboration between academic, government, and innovation actors, and expediting the transfer of research into practical solutions.

4.4. Incentives and barriers to technology transfer

For academia, there are various funding opportunities through EU programmes such as Digital Europe, Horizon Europe and European Defence Fund. These mechanisms provide concrete opportunities to scale innovation and turn research into deployable solutions. NATO's Defence Innovation Accelerator for the North Atlantic (DIANA) also creates strong initiatives by opening international test centres and accelerators, linking Lithuanian innovators with allied defence ecosystems.

National Coordination Centre (NCC) under the MoD also provides grants (from the Digital Europe and national funds) to Lithuanian SMEs to implement various projects related to research, development, and innovation in the field of cybersecurity.

According to interview participants, in addition to developing technologies for preventing, detecting, and mitigating cyberattacks, there is a need of methods and tools to evaluate cybersecurity effectiveness in terms of awareness levels, regulatory compliance, incident response times, etc. at all levels (organization, sector, national). This will help not only to understand current situation but also to plan next steps for increasing national cybersecurity protection level.

Key incentives for engaging in cybersecurity technology transfer include national defence contribution, practical validation of innovations, and innovation recognition. These transfers allow testing of cutting-edge tools, strengthening collaboration with universities, government, and industry, and enhancing Lithuania's overall technological advancement.

However, there are numerous barriers to technology transfer, including:

- Bureaucratic approval processes and lack of consistent rules for all participants and a clear certification process required for transferring cybersecurity technologies.
- Restrictions for using certain technologies for organizations in critical infrastructure domain. E.g., they cannot use some technologies developed in China in some other countries. So, there are some constraints and limitations.

- Rapid change of cybersecurity requirements. In the cybersecurity area, you must develop products fast. If you are slow, if you have long processes to get permission etc., your product is already useless when developed. So, this is a big challenge, especially for universities.
- Shortage of skilled professionals, capable to develop technologies.
- Limited funding for prototyping.
- Fragmented communication between stakeholders.
- Legislative barriers. Some public organizations are unable to participate in EU grant applications due to strict procurement regulations. As a result, while funding opportunities exist, access to them is often restricted by legislative barriers. This should be simplified.
- For many organizations, lack of funding remains a major issue – they may have great ideas and the willingness to act, but insufficient resources to bring them to life.
- Using AI in both civilian and military sectors is a big challenge due to the adoption of the EU AI Act in 2024 (EU Reg 2024/1689, 2024), which will become fully applicable in 2026. Civilian technologies will require full compliance with this law, while military technologies that use AI will have exemptions, however it will be difficult to develop and train them by civilian companies.
- A need for a cultural shift in the military domain. Sometimes military operations are understood in the old-fashioned ways – protecting the nation by using military planes, tanks, armoured vehicles, etc. However, recently, NATO is taking the advantage of digital transformation – trying to reach the same effects by using digital technologies, including cyber. Therefore, culturally we need to understand that there are other innovative ways in achieving the same goal by employment of different type of technologies, which might not be so expensive.

Survey participants have ranked the factors that are the main barriers to cybersecurity technology transfer in Lithuania in the following way:

- Lack of trust among stakeholders (71%);
- Lack of government funding programmes (64%);

- Lack of public-private partnerships (61%);
- Insufficient resources (57%);
- Technical incompatibilities (50%);
- Legal constraints (18%).

4.5. Examples of successful technology transfer initiatives

One of the successful initiatives is the launch of the Vytis program (EIMIN, 2025a). This initiative comes from Ministry of Economy and Innovation and Innovation Agency. This initiative is aimed at strengthening the country's defence industry capabilities, promoting innovation and increasing international competitiveness. 300 million euros have been allocated for this purpose. This is the first initiative of its kind aimed at strengthening the defence sector and developing new technologies that can later be applied in other sectors. The Vytis consortium consists of the Kaunas Science and Technology Park, the project initiator and coordinator; the Innovation Agency; the Inland Waterways Directorate; Vytautas Magnus University; the Lithuanian Riflemen's Union; and the Lithuanian Energy Institute (EIMIN, 2025b).

One key element of the Vytis program is the Defense Innovation Vouchers program, which has already allocated €1 million, and invitations to use the Miltech Sandbox infrastructure for technology testing and prototyping. In the fall of 2025, the Innovation Agency, together with the Lithuanian Armed Forces, is organizing the Miltech Academy. This multi-day program is designed to provide representatives of defence and security companies, research centres, and the armed forces with knowledge and skills in the field of defence innovation.

An example of successful technology transfer is the DNS Firewall – a free public DNS (Domain Name System) service with additional security features for residents and organisations, developed by NCSC in cooperation with the Internet Service Centre DOMREG at Kaunas University of Technology (KTU).

The Defence Investment Fund has been established in 2025 with the total of €40 million allocated to it for investing in innovative companies in the fields of defence and security. The Fund was established following the signing of a financing agreement between ILTE and the Ministries of National Defence, and Economy and Innovation of the Republic of Lithuania.

In defence sector, there are many initiatives and success stories of cybersecurity technology transfer. NATO has a huge initiative for transferring AI technologies to classified systems. In the near future, it will enhance our decision-making ability by leveraging these technologies in conducting military operations.

Another example for NATO is quantum computing – one of the emerging and disruptive technologies. This technology could transform our way of doing the business. For now, data protection algorithms used in a private and public sector have been resilient. But our adversaries are developing quantum technologies at significant pace and currently widely-used algorithms could be breached. And if this happens, we will have a huge problem, as our society and all sectors rely on them – from bank transfers to registry, etc. In response to this, NATO has been working on various initiatives that employ quantum technologies in creating different quantum-resistant algorithms.

Cybersecurity technology transfer strengthens Lithuania's national security by driving innovation and operational capability. Initiatives like the Riftenem Union Lizdeika company integrate research outputs such as network monitoring and secure communications into real-world exercises. The MitreEN Sandbox, created with the Innovation Agency and partners, has improved the ability to turn research into deployable solutions. Most initiatives are cybersecurity exercises and events, both national and international, providing opportunities to share, test, and adopt knowledge. Improvement is still needed in commercial-academic collaboration and procurement processes for defence-tech prototypes.

Additional successful examples include EW-resistant networks based on LoRa used in sensors and ATAK, Stirling cycle generators for frontline use increasing energy resilience,

widespread adoption of cybersecurity hygiene in the Riflemen Union Lizdeika company that became mandatory courses, ATAK operator training, hardened portable devices, and various drone operation doctrines. Success was achieved through multidisciplinary collaboration involving software engineers, electronics experts, and defence volunteers working together under real operational conditions, alongside motivated leadership and real operational conditions.

5. Information sharing mechanisms

This section examines how cybersecurity-related knowledge, threat intelligence, and best practices are shared between national and international stakeholders. It evaluates the effectiveness of current information-sharing platforms and highlights areas where improvements are needed.

5.1. Existing national cybersecurity information-sharing policies and frameworks

The Cybersecurity Law states that cybersecurity entities or other users of the Cyber Security Information System have to exchange data related to cyber incidents, cyber threats, near misses, and other relevant information through the Cyber Security Information System. Currently, this is the main tool managed by the NCSC, which is designed not only for exchanging of information and reporting cyber incidents, but also for performing various other functions.

As the register of cybersecurity entities was only established in April 2025, the effectiveness of this platform has not yet been assessed. The institutions implementing cybersecurity policy are required to cooperate under the Cyber Security Act (Article 20), which is being done successfully.

NCSC is responsible for implementing the Cybersecurity Law that regulates information sharing. Regulation is quite thorough; sharing is based on the agreement among

institutions. Sometimes, when an organization has something that it does not want to share, it does not do it. But the framework is in place, and we are quite mature, the policies and tools are in place. However, actual information sharing is still a challenge. For critical entities, it is mandatory to share information in accordance with the law, but it is up to organization to decide if it wants to share the information. So far, NCSC does not have power or authority to intervene in companies' business and force them to do it yet.

Also, companies cannot share the data directly with each other but need to go through the centralized system. This is a big challenge, especially for the financial institutions, since they cannot inform others about what happened, about different threats, they just need to inform the responsible institution. They do not have any right to send the data to other financial institutions, because most of this data is personal data and cannot be shared.

5.2. Cybersecurity threat intelligence sharing mechanisms, platforms and tools

Survey participants reported on the following mechanisms used by their organizations for threat intelligence sharing: National CERT (71%); Informal networks (50%); Private threat intelligence platforms (46%); and ISACs (11%).

At the European level, MoD and NCSC are part of ENISA and the EU CERTs. They have the legal rights and obligations to share data, such as statistical and incidents' data. They need to act immediately, inform neighbours and so on. Lithuania uses the same Internet infrastructure in EU, the same hubs, so it is crucial to inform each other immediately when incidents occur.

At the national level, NCSC coordinates information sharing through Malware Information Sharing Platform (MISP) platform – an open-source threat intelligence and sharing platform. It is used not only to register the information of incidents that happened, but also to exchange the information with its clients – different institutions, police, and other agencies about the cyber incidents. In addition, if NKSC is aware of good practices on how to deal with certain incidents, it can make this information accessible to its clients through

the platform. Based on this information, they could configure their systems to patch the vulnerabilities.

MISP platform is part of the Cyber Security Information System (CSIS) toolkit, which is available for all cybersecurity entities in Lithuania and includes additional tools such as Sandbox, Chat platform, lists of blocked IPs and domains, and technical cybersecurity measures data.

Furthermore, different critical infrastructure sectors use platforms specific to their sector. E.g., in energy sector, organizations from Lithuania have a platform to cooperate with colleagues in Latvia, Estonia, Poland in information sharing.

At the higher education institution level, we have Litnet for sharing data not only within Lithuania but also with higher education institutions in other European countries. We have the Eduroam network to which educational institutions are connected, and it is also used to share data, such as traffic, viruses, technical threats, etc.

In addition, we have an International civ-mil cyber threat analysis platform – Regional Cyber Defence Centre (under the NCSC). The Centre team produces daily and weekly cyber threat assessments and situation reports. Daily reports are shared with RCDC member states; weekly reports are shared with broader community of Lithuanian critical infrastructure subjects and international like-minded partners (200+ contacts worldwide). International experts work on a rotation basis from member countries (Ukrainian experts currently work at the centre full-time; more than 20 US (PANG) personnel visits of experts for 1-2 week rotations over 4 years; 2025 second half – Czech Republic and Poland expert rotations expected). From the establishment RCDC produced over 7 studies, over 150 weekly reports and more than 500 daily reports.

Military has its own channels too (classified). It collects information from different organizations by using various channels, then fuses it and generate situation awareness reports, beneficial for everyone.

Although all abovementioned mechanisms are effective, but their success depends on the preparedness and technical expertise of the users.

5.3. International cooperation and best practices in cybersecurity information sharing

International cooperation involves information sharing with NATO, ENISA, cybersecurity incident response team networks, where threat intelligence sharing is the key element.

International collaboration depends on the topic. E.g., to raise the awareness, NCSC communicates through CSIRT with other countries when Lithuania was switching from BRELL to European energy grid. So, during that process NCSC was on a higher alert, and constantly exchanged information with our partners if something was happening. NCSC wants to further foster international collaboration in the cyber threat intelligence field to have a better understanding about cyber threats in different countries and regions.

RCDC is actively involved in sharing cybersecurity-related information internationally. One of the examples is the International Cyber is a Comparative study of Russian Cyber Offensive Capabilities from 2022 to 2025. The study was made together with other partners, mainly the US and Ukraine, and shows how Russia's cyber ecosystem expanded and advanced. Other reports produced by RCDC with partners worth to note are 3 major cyber threat research studies published: "Report on How to Recognize China Cyber Threats", "Report on Cyber Threats for the Critical Infrastructure in the Baltic Sea Region" and "Report on Cyber Lessons Learned During the War in Ukraine".

In the energy sector, a good international collaboration examples include ENTSO-E (European Network of Transmission System Operators) and EU CSIRTs network.

There is collaboration with Interpol as well. One example is the recent cyberattack on one of Lithuanian universities, when Interpol was very helpful to get the information about other similar attacks, which enabled the university to recover the encrypted information. University was able to reverse engineer the algorithm and decrypt the information

encrypted by the attackers. Without the information on other similar attacks, it was almost impossible to do so. So, the information sharing was really beneficial on this occasion.

There are several ongoing research projects on international collaboration, involving Lithuanian universities, such as, e.g., SOCCER (Security Operation Centre in the Central Europe Region) project. It brings together nine partners from five countries (Poland, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Estonia and Lithuania). Project is aimed at developing a dedicated system for continuously sharing incident and traffic data.

Another example is the CyberHubs project, aimed at addressing the shortage of cybersecurity professionals in Europe by developing an efficient and collaborative European network of multi-stakeholder cybersecurity skills incubators. There are seven European countries involved in this project, including Belgium, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Lithuania, Slovenia, and Spain. As the result of this project, cybersecurity hubs will be created in each country and interconnected into network to enable collaboration and information sharing.

In defence sector, international cooperation, such as participation in Locked Shields (annual exercise, organised by NATO CCDCOE since 2010, to train cybersecurity experts to enhance their skills in defending national IT systems and critical infrastructure under real-time attacks) and similar exercises, has provided practical experience and access to broader threat intelligence and subject matter knowledge. These collaborations have been beneficial in testing and improving national cybersecurity capabilities.

Survey results showed that 50% of participants' organizations have participated in international information sharing initiatives. Examples of successful experiences include International and domestic cybersecurity projects by academic institutions, and information sharing by national and international law firms to collect and systemize European data on NIS2 directive implementation. Also, successful use of MISP platform by NATO, EU, and national organizations.

5.4. Challenges in cross-sectoral information sharing

To enable successful information sharing, it is important for organization to see the benefits of information sharing to be willing to do it. E.g., if one organization has a problem, it will be willing to share information, because it can get the information back of how other organizations solved similar problems. However, many organizations are still quite passive due to the lack of trust and risk of potential damage to reputation or even financial losses.

Lack of trust is the main challenge for successful cross-sectoral information sharing. The main principle of cybersecurity is trust, while the main instrument for ensuring cybersecurity is zero-trust. So, we don't trust each other and sometimes it is difficult to get information even about simple incidents from different stakeholders, both national and international. We also don't want to show anybody that we are vulnerable, and we want to maintain our reputation. But this does not help to protect others.

In addition to trust, there are other challenges related to difference between sectors. First, the relevance of information. E.g., some indicators could be relevant in banking sector, but not in energy sector, as they operate in different environment. So, some indicators are not from other sectors are not always useful. Another aspect is the security of indicators. Some entities could not share the indicators of compromises because that information is considered as classified. The final aspect is the lack of common understanding of how to classify different indicators. E.g., some sectors consider Google as malicious because it is prohibited to use Google within their environment. So, different sectors – different understanding, different taxonomies and thresholds.

It is very important to enable cross-sectoral communication and sharing of threat intelligence and attack vectors. If one attack vector is relevant to the financial sectors, it could happen that in a couple of months or a year we will see the same vector in manufacturing. So, we need to have cooperation between sectors. One challenge is trust, also having a secure platform for that and sharing sensitive information. In addition, sharing information about indicators of compromise is very important as well. According to

interview participants, hackers are lazy, they can simply change one element in the malware, and the detection tool or technology might not detect it. But if you have research and development team and you will invest in indicators of compromise, you will have a really proactive way to detect attacks.

In private sector, the main challenge is the sensitivity of information, and the unwillingness of companies to share that information, because it can impact their business. It is also challenging due to commercial secrecy and various restrictions from all sides. There are reputation-related issues as well. Nobody wants to talk about the bad things. And usually in cybersecurity, you have to share the bad thing – that something went wrong at your company or with your customers.

Furthermore, there is a fear of loss of control over your information – as soon as organization transfers information, control of it is lost. E.g., government and friendly civilian entity might control the organization. However, part or whole organization could be sold to another company, let's assume not so friendly, and information that had been given to that organization might end up in wrong hands. So, trust is a big challenge for information sharing. When sharing, we need to consider all associated risks and sometimes it is very difficult to make a proper decision.

Survey results confirmed the abovementioned findings. Lack of trust between sectors was mentioned as the greatest challenge (79%), followed by Technical incompatibilities (46%), Insufficient resources (39%), and Legal or regulatory barriers (36%). One more interesting observation provided by survey participants was that cyber institutions often tend to run a 'silos' style organisational culture, when departments or teams operate in isolation, failing to share information.

5.5. Other informal information and knowledge sharing instruments

MoD implements formal and informal cybersecurity information sharing in various ways:

- Participating in various formal working groups and other formal activities, established by national institutions (e.g. Cyber Security Council), EU and/or NATO;
- Bilateral and multilateral cooperation with other countries' institutions and organizations that implement cybersecurity policy, as well as other international organizations could be also an example where cybersecurity information is shared.
- In addition, informal cooperation also takes place in the form of joint projects with business entities, scientific and academic institutions, non-governmental organizations and cybersecurity entities. NCSC frequently shared the information informally. E.g., if it finds some data stolen from an organization, it informs them right away by email without formal letters. Informal communication helps to gain trust between organizations, different partners and even different countries, that's why not only the formal, but also informal exchange of information is important.

Cybersecurity entities benefit from informal information sharing using the Chat tool provided by NCSC, as well as the bilateral channels with colleagues from other entities. This is a very beneficial way, because someone on the other side assesses if the information could be relevant and beneficial to your organization. This is a common practice between critical entities and regulators.

There is a lot of cybersecurity-related information, and sometimes it is difficult to determine which information is useful for your organization. It would be great to have more relevant information. We have a good example – Ukraine's CERT. They publish in their website, on Russia's Advanced Persistent Threat (APT) campaigns publicly. And that information is very beneficial, because it includes tactics, techniques, procedures, and indicators. And this information is relevant to other Eastern European countries as well. So, this is a great example how different organizations should share information. Also, e.g., if CSIRT in Ukraine has reported on some tools that have been used for cyberattacks and those tools are publicly available, other organizations can try to use those tools by to check if your systems are vulnerable or not.

Cybersecurity community is currently quite small in Lithuania, most of members know each other, so it is common to call each other and share cybersecurity-related information informally, person-to-person. Sometimes using the formal channels takes a lot of time due to bureaucracy, and in case of cybersecurity incidents, you have to react quickly. So, using informal communication with your personal contacts helps to speed up some tasks. Due to sensitivity of information, phone calls or in-person meetings are preferred to the online meetings.

A successful example is the recent cyberattack on one of Lithuanian universities. Since IT-department members at different universities know each other, they immediately communicated with each other, which helped to prevent the attacks on other universities. This type of communication is very beneficial – it is not involving sharing of personal data but sharing incident data and advising on what to do to stay protected.

In military organizations, informal information sharing happens all the time using various channels for doing that, such as a phone call or email from a colleague abroad. If one organization finds something interesting, or experience something unusual in its information systems, it shares this information informally, if it thinks that it might be useful to others. In addition, since military organizations in Lithuania are part of collective NATO Defence, thus they are continuously cooperating not only formally, but also informally through various channels – meetings, conferences, emails, and one-to-one calls.

Survey participants identified four the most commonly used channels in their organizations for informal information sharing: Professional associations (71%), Personal networks (71%), Social Media Platforms (39%), and Industry conferences (29%).

6. Analysis of dual-use technologies

This section explores the intersection between cybersecurity technologies that have applications in both civilian and defence contexts. It discusses the implications of dual-use technologies for national security, innovation, and regulatory compliance.

6.1. Definition and importance of dual-use cybersecurity technologies

There are a lot of dual-use cybersecurity technologies, as most of computer hardware and software technologies can be applied in both civilian and defence sectors. Many advanced technologies very likely have been created for the defence sector first, and only after several years they become available for civilians. It is a traditional way of developing the technologies.

Military sector benefits from the development in civilian sector as well, as they are experts in technology development, which can be applied for military use. E.g., many civilian organizations provide security software, from vulnerability detection to penetration testing. Some software could be used for military purposes. This is especially relevant for advancement in developing emerging technologies, such as AI, quantum technologies, hypersonic systems, etc., where expertise is on the civilian side.

In our national business ecosystem, waste of resources is simply not feasible. Dual-use products are the only way to go, as the services and solutions must not only work as part of national defence but must also be able to sustain themselves in an open market when government contracts are not available. Tools developed for civilian infrastructure such as encrypted communication networks or intrusion detection platforms can be adapted for military use. Balancing accessibility and security ensures both economic growth and stronger national defence capabilities.

The majority of survey participants also think that dual-use technologies are important (41%), very important (37%), or extremely important (14%) in their organizations' operations.

According to interviewees, there are some legal challenges related to the development of dual-use technologies, since regulations provide more freedom for developing technologies for defence purposes as compared to civilian use. One example is the use of AI, regulated by the EU AI Act. It is not possible to create technology based on AI, which

uses biometrical scanning and real time tracking for civilian use. However, there are exceptions for the defence sector. This puts technology developers in difficult situation. They can create AI systems to recognize people; however, they cannot train them using the pictures of actual people. At the same time, we know that our police and national security agencies need such technologies. So that's a legal problem – how can you create technology if you are not allowed to do it? Thus, more effort is needed to define legal aspects of dual-use technology development and use.

6.2. National policies and frameworks governing dual-use cybersecurity solutions

EU has dedicated dual-use regulation, adopted in 2021 (EU Reg 2021/821, 2021). Nationally, we have our Export Control policies. In 2024, the Lithuanian Government has approved a proposal to amend the National List of Controlled Dual-Use Goods to restrict the export from Lithuania to third countries of goods that could be utilised in Russia's military aggression against Ukraine (Lithuanian Government, 2024). These amendments are also aimed at reducing threats to the security of Lithuanian society.

6.3. Challenges in regulating and managing dual-use technologies

Companies developing dual-use technologies are not allowed to sell anything to the third countries if they are not NATO or EU members. It is a big headache for Lithuanian companies, getting licenses is difficult. Meanwhile, selling technology locally for the defence sector is well define and not that complicated.

There is a lack of commonly agreed procedure on how to use defence technologies in civilian sector, especially by critical infrastructure organizations, without risking damaging the systems, because some of the tools are intrusive and can do a lot of damage to operational technology systems and devices.

There are some challenges related to licensing. Sometimes for acquiring cybersecurity tools for military use, it is necessary to get a license, and licensing could come from different countries, such as US, UK, Germany, etc. It takes time to get specific license, because technology-producing nation controls these technologies and wants to be sure that it will be used under certain conditions, it wants to protect own interests. Nations consider very carefully what technologies could be transferred to military organizations and when and need to have the necessary controls in place.

Balancing open research with operational confidentiality remains a key difficulty when technologies can serve both civil and defence roles.

Survey participants identified the following challenges that hinder effective regulation and management of dual-use cybersecurity technologies: Legal or regulatory barriers (57%); Technological complexities (54%); Ethical considerations (39%); and Lack of international cooperation (29%).

6.4. Examples of cybersecurity technologies with dual-use applications

Dual-use technology examples include Metasploit, Mimikatz, also some tools in Windows environment that could also be used for dual-use purposes, like PowerShell, Netcat, etc. Also, Cobalt Strike, which is popular among attackers, and Kali Linux operating system, which is also publicly available.

In addition, real-time tracking systems, aimed at detecting hybrid threats, can be used for both civilian and military purposes. Development effort of such tool is currently ongoing, involving Lithuanian universities. Another aspect is encryption and secure data transmission. There are solutions for sending sensitive data securely, which could be of dual-use. Also, some monitoring systems, e.g., that are using drones, could be used for civilian and military applications. Furthermore, the security operation centres, SOCs, could serve not public institutions and commercial organizations, but military as well. If we had good platform and trust for sharing, we could have a dual-use process.

Other examples of dual-use technologies include secure LoRa communication systems, EW-resistant wireless tools, AI-assisted image recognition for UAV reconnaissance, Stirling cycle generators for energy resilience and power supply supplements, and cyber-hardened IoT sensor networks. Their dual nature comes from being equally useful in civilian emergency response such as wildfire monitoring and defence applications such as tactical awareness. The adaptability and modular architecture of these tools make them effective across both domains.

Survey participants identified the following cybersecurity technologies with dual-use applications used in Lithuania: Secunet, Palpo Alto Networks, Cisco, penetration testing, red teaming, phishing simulation tools, such as e.g., nmap, metasploit, GoPhish.

NATO has various dual-use technology applications such as e.g., cloud computing. NATO has civilian contractors, they are collaborating with Amazon, Google, Microsoft and run common projects, thus creating classified cloud computing environments. This is an example of dual-use technology, as cloud is very popular in civilian sector and many organizations are using it by migrating their business to cloud. As well as, this technology is also used for military purposes, since our processes are very similar. Like civilian organizations, military organizations have goals, functions, processes, management structures. Therefore, they need similar technologies to do their job.

7. Recommendations

This chapter presents targeted recommendations derived from the analysis of Lithuania's cybersecurity landscape, technology transfer mechanisms, information-sharing practices, and dual-use technology governance.

The suggestions are designed to inform policymakers, industry stakeholders, academic institutions, and civil society actors, facilitating the advancement of national cybersecurity objectives.

7.1. Strengthening national cybersecurity governance

Recommendation 1: There is a need to operationalize the enforcement the Cybersecurity Law to ensure that all cybersecurity entities comply with it, especially with regards to information sharing.

Recommendation 2: There is a need of cybersecurity policies and guidelines for all organizations in the country, not only identified cybersecurity entities, which are covered by the Cybersecurity Law.

Recommendation 3: Due to the current geopolitical situation in Lithuania and the region, more attention needs to be given to hybrid threats, which could include a combination of antagonistic activities, such as cyberattacks, information manipulation, economic influence and military threats among others. Thus, there is a need for an appropriate “hybrid” approaches to defend against hybrid threats.

7.2. Enhancing Technology Transfer Mechanisms

Recommendation 4: Consistent rules for all participants and a clear certification process required for transferring cybersecurity technologies need to be defined.

7.3. Improving information sharing practices

Recommendation 5: There is a need to establishing novel ways to increase trust among organizations for successful information sharing.

Recommendation 6: To enhance international collaboration and information sharing, there is a need to have a unified framework which would be acceptable in all countries. Currently, it is undermined due to the differences in legal frameworks between countries.

7.4. Managing dual-use cybersecurity technologies

Recommendation 7: There is a need to perform policy review and regulatory impact analysis on dual-use technologies and propose guidance to aid developers with dual-use technology transfer.

7.5. Capacity building and awareness

Recommendation 8: Education system must be revised to include cybersecurity education from the young age (primary schools) up to university level and beyond (life-long-learning). This implies updating the study programmes at schools, colleges, and universities in a harmonized way to include cybersecurity training.

Recommendation 9: Public awareness is still low, while general population is continuously getting more vulnerable to cyberattacks, especially to social engineering attacks. New effective ways to educate people of different age groups are urgently needed, especially young people, who have extensive online presence and low cybersecurity risk awareness, and elderly people with low digital skills, who are often the victims of social engineering attacks.

Recommendation 10: This is the most important recommendation of this study – lack of cybersecurity skills is extreme and needs to be addressed at the national level. NCSC, the government, academia, and organizations need to work together and come up with an action plan to prepare and train people to become cybersecurity professionals in a short time to address urgent shortage of skilled cybersecurity professionals in Lithuania.

8. Conclusions

This national case study has provided an in-depth analysis of Lithuania's cybersecurity landscape, focusing on technology transfer mechanisms, information-sharing practices, and the governance of dual-use technologies. Through a combination of desk research, stakeholder interviews, and surveys, we've identified both strengths and areas for improvement in the nation's approach to cybersecurity.

Most of the case study participants were satisfied with the national cybersecurity strategy and agreed that it was quite effective. Lithuania has adopted a centralised approach to cybersecurity: it has one single ministry responsible for cybersecurity – Ministry of National Défense, which has all subordinate organizations, operating under it, including the National Cyber Security Centre, capable of ensuring cybersecurity in a timely and coordinated way. Furthermore, Lithuania has updated its Cybersecurity Law to include NIS 2 Directive in October 2024. Its implementation is progressing successfully under the supervision of the National Cyber Security Centre.

Lithuania is actively participating in international cooperation in cybersecurity through the activities of the Regional Cyber Defence Centre under the Ministry of National Defence, also through collaboration with ENISA, NATO, and other international partners. There is also active collaboration with international colleagues at the sector level. According to interview and survey participants, such collaborations are very useful to enhance Lithuania's cybersecurity capabilities, however, the difference in legal frameworks between countries could be a challenge.

Most of interview and survey participants agreed that cybersecurity technology transfer was important for advancing cybersecurity capabilities in Lithuania. However, currently, few cybersecurity technologies are being developed nationally due to various reasons, such as the lack of government funding and public-private partnerships. In most cases, organizations use the technologies available in the market. According to some participants, there is no shortage of cybersecurity technologies, but rather a significant shortage of skilled professionals able to use and maintain those technologies, which must be urgently addressed. The situation could change due to the arrival of emergent technologies, such as AI and quantum computing, which could be used by malicious actors. This will require the development of novel cybersecurity technologies.

Information sharing nationally is managed by the National Cyber Security Centre, which provides the dedicated platform for this purpose. Lack of trust is the main factor hindering information sharing. Instead, informal information sharing with trusted contacts is widely practiced.

There were various cybersecurity-related challenges identified during case study as well. The biggest and the most urgent challenge is the shortage of skilled cybersecurity professionals. In addition, there are challenges in assuring cybersecurity due to the use of emergent technologies, such as AI, by malicious actors. Furthermore, there is an increase in cyber and hybrid threats due to the current geopolitical situation and the proximity of hostile neighbours. Additional challenges include limited resources, insufficient funding, the use of legacy systems, and the lack of public awareness among others.

In summary, Lithuania has good cybersecurity foundation. The findings of this case study highlight Lithuania's strong institutional foundations and commitment to cybersecurity. The next phase should focus on translating policy frameworks into operational capacity and ensuring long-term sustainability through human capital development. Next steps should focus on its operationalization, skills development and raising of public awareness.

9. References

Benetis, V. (2025). *Cybersecurity@Lithuania Map*. Version 2025-09-03. <https://github.com/vibenas/Cybersecurity-Lithuania-Map>

Bukauskas, L., Brilingaitė, A., Ikamas, K., Juozapavičius, A., & Lepaitė, D. (2022). *Development of the national cybersecurity competence map*. <https://doi.org/10.15388/CIBERSEK.2022>

EIMIN. (2025a). "Vytis" initiative: €300 million to boost defence industry. Ministry of the Economy and Innovation (EIMIN). <https://eimin.lrv.lt/en/structure-and-contacts/news-1/vytis-initiative-300-million-to-boost-defence-industry/>

EIMIN. (2025b). EIMIN: A centre for the development and testing of defence and security innovations is being established. Ministry of the Economy and Innovation (EIMIN). <https://eimin.lrv.lt/en/structure-and-contacts/news-1/eimin-a-centre-for-the-development-and-testing-of-defence-and-security-innovations-is-being-established-4sRU/>

ENISA. (2022). *ECSF – European Cybersecurity Skills Framework*. September 2022. <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/european-cybersecurity-skills-framework-role-profiles>

EU Reg 910/2014. (2014, July 23). Consolidated text: Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 July 2014 on electronic identification and trust services for electronic transactions in the internal market and repealing Directive

1999/93/EC. *Official Journal of the European Union*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3AO2014R0910-20241018>

EU Reg 2019/881. (2019, April 17). Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act). *Official Journal of the European Union*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32019R0881>

EU Reg 2021/887. (2021, May 20). Regulation (EU) 2021/887 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 establishing the European Cybersecurity Industrial, Technology and Research Competence Centre and the Network of National Coordination Centres. *Official Journal of the European Union*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32021R0887>

EU Reg 2021/821. (2021, May 20) Regulation (EU) 2021/821 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 setting up a Union regime for the control of exports, brokering, technical assistance, transit and transfer of dual-use items. *Official Journal of the European Union*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2021/821/oj/eng>

EU Reg 2022/2554. (2022, December 14). Regulation (EU) 2022/2554 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on digital operational resilience for the financial sector and amending Regulations (EC) No 1060/2009, (EU) No 648/2012, (EU) No 600/2014, (EU) No 909/2014 and (EU) 2016/1011 (Text with EEA relevance). *Official Journal of the European Union*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/2554/oj/eng>

EU Dir 2022/2555. (2022, December 14). Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and Directive (EU) 2018/1972, and repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148 (NIS 2 Directive). *Official Journal of the European Union*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2022/2555>

EU Reg 2024/1689. (2024, June 13). Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act) (Text with EEA relevance). *Official Journal of the European Union*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj/eng>

European Council. (2025). Hybrid threats. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/hybrid-threats/>

France 24. (2025). Lithuania accuses Belarus of 'hybrid attack' after contraband balloons shut airports. <https://www.france24.com/en/europe/20251027-lithuania-balloon-incursion-hybrid-attack>

Juozapavicius, A. (2025). Resilience to cyber threats: Strategies to counter cyber threats in small states. In Smaliukiene, R., Schultz, D., & Giedraityte, V. (Eds.). *Democratic Resilience in the Baltics, Vol. 2: Societal Resilience as a Defensive Power*. Springer

Lithuanian Government. (2024). Strengthening national control measures. Government of the Republic of Lithuania. <https://lrv.lt/en/news/strengthening-national-control-measures/>

MoD. (2025a). Overview of the Cybersecurity Status in Lithuania: Key Information 2024. Ministry of the National Defence of Lithuania. https://kam.lt/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/Overview-of-the-Cybersecurity-status_LT_2024.pdf

MoD. (2025b). Lithuania's defence industry development. Ministry of the National Defence of Lithuania. <https://kam.lt/en/lithuanias-defence-industry-development/>

Official Statistics Portal. (2025) Lithuanian official statistics portal. <https://osp.stat.gov.lt/>

RCDC. (2024). Cyber Threats to Critical Infrastructure in the Baltic Sea Region. Regional Cyber Defence Centre, Lithuania. https://www.nksc.lt/doc/rkgc/2024_Cyber_Threats_to_Critical_Infrastructure_in_the_Baltic_Sea_region.pdf

Republic of Lithuania. (2014, December 11). The Law on Cyber Security. <https://www.e-tar.lt/portal/en/legalAct/5468a25089ef11e4a98a9f2247652cf4>

Republic of Lithuania. (2018, August 13). National Cyber Security Strategy. https://ccdcoe.org/uploads/2018/10/Lithuania_Cyber-Security-Strategy-2018_English.pdf

Stitilis, D., Laurinaitis, M., Malinauskaite, I., & Warren, M. (2024). Navigating the Cyber Front: Belarus' State Control and Emerging Cyber Threats. European Conference on Cyber Warfare and Security. 23. 542-561. 10.34190/eccws.23.1.2518.

10. Annexes

This section includes any additional supporting documents, data, or reference materials that provide further context for the case study.

Annex 1 – In-depth interview questionnaire

Question 1:

From your perspective, how does cybersecurity technology transfer contribute to enhancing national security and resilience in [Country Name]? Could you provide examples of successful initiatives or highlight areas needing improvement?

Purpose:

This open-ended question encourages stakeholders to share detailed insights and specific examples, facilitating a deeper understanding of the practical implications and challenges of cybersecurity technology transfer within the national context.

Question 2:

In your opinion, how effectively the current national cybersecurity strategy has been implemented so far?

Question 3:

Which organisations play a pivotal role in your country's cybersecurity ecosystem, and how do they collaborate to address cybersecurity challenges?

Question 4:

What are the most pressing cybersecurity challenges facing your country, and what measures are being taken to address them?

Question 5:

How does your country engage in international cybersecurity cooperation, and what benefits or challenges have arisen from these partnerships?

Question 6:

How do you define technology transfer in the context of cybersecurity, and why is it important for your organization or sector?

Question 7:

Can you elaborate on the legal and regulatory frameworks that facilitate or hinder cybersecurity technology transfer in your country?

Question 8:

Which national institutions are most actively involved in cybersecurity technology transfer, and how do they collaborate to facilitate this process?

Question 9:

What are the primary incentives your organization faces in participating in cybersecurity technology transfer?

Question 10:

What are the primary barriers your organization faces in participating in cybersecurity technology transfer?

Question 11:

Can you share examples of successful cybersecurity technology transfer initiatives your organization has been involved in, and what factors contributed to their success?

Question 12:

Can you describe the national policies or frameworks in place for cybersecurity information sharing, and how effectively they function in practice?

Question 13:

Which platforms or tools does your organization use for sharing and receiving cybersecurity threat intelligence, and how effective are they?

Question 14:

Can you share experiences of international cooperation in cybersecurity information sharing that have benefited your organization?

Question 15:

What challenges has your organization faced in sharing cybersecurity information with partners from other sectors?

Question 16:

Does your organization engage in informal cybersecurity information sharing? If so, through which channels, and how valuable are these interactions?

Question 17:

How does your organization perceive the role of dual-use cybersecurity technologies in balancing national security and innovation?

Question 18:

Can you elaborate on the national policies or frameworks that regulate dual-use cybersecurity technologies, and how effectively they function in practice?

Question 19:

What challenges has your organization faced in regulating or managing dual-use cybersecurity technologies?

Question 20:

Can you share examples of cybersecurity technologies with dual-use applications your organization has developed or utilized, and what factors contributed to their dual-use nature?

Annex 2 – Online survey

Question 1:

Which sector do you represent?

- Public government
- Private sector
- Academic/ research Institution
- Civil society
- Military related organisation
- Other (please specify)

Question 2:

Which type of institution do you represent?

- o Government agency
- o Research institution
- o Private sector company
- o Non-Governmental Organization
- o Military related organisation
- o Other (please specify)

Question 3:

On a scale from 1 (Not Important) to 5 (Extremely Important), how important is international collaboration in cybersecurity for your organisation?

Purpose:

This Likert-scale question quantifies the perceived importance of international collaboration, allowing for statistical analysis across different stakeholder groups and countries.

Question 4:

On a scale of 1 (Not Effective) to 5 (Highly Effective), how would you rate the implementation of the national cybersecurity strategy in your country?

Question 5:

Which of the following areas do you consider to be the most significant challenges in your country's cybersecurity landscape? (Select up to three)

- Lack of skilled professionals
- Insufficient funding
- Inadequate legal frameworks Portal
- Poor inter-agency coordination
- Limited public awareness
- Other (please specify)

Question 6:

To what extent does international cooperation enhance your country's cybersecurity capabilities?

- Not at all
- To a small extent
- To a moderate extent
- To a great extent
- To a very great extent

Question 7:

On a scale from 1 (Not Important) to 5 (Extremely Important), how important is technology transfer in advancing cybersecurity capabilities in your country?

Question 8:

How familiar are you with the national legal frameworks governing cybersecurity technology transfer?

- Not at all familiar
- Slightly familiar
- Moderately familiar
- Very familiar
- Extremely familiar

Question 9:

Which of the following factors act as barriers to cybersecurity technology transfer in your country? (Select all that apply)

- Lack of government funding programmes
- Lack of public-private partnerships
- Legal constraints
- Lack of trust among stakeholders
- Insufficient resources
- technical incompatibilities
- Other (please specify)

Question 10:

Are you aware of any successful cybersecurity technology transfer initiatives in your country?

- Yes
- No
- If yes, please provide a brief description:

Question 11:

How familiar are you with your country's cybersecurity information-sharing policies and frameworks?

- Not at all familiar
- Slightly familiar
- Moderately familiar
- Very familiar
- Extremely familiar

Question 12:

Which of the following mechanisms does your organization utilize for cybersecurity threat intelligence sharing? (Select all that apply)

- National CERT
- ISACs

- Private threat intelligence platforms
- Informal networks
- Other (please specify)

Question 13:

Has your organization participated in international cybersecurity information-sharing initiatives?

- Yes
- No
- If yes, please specify

Question 14:

Which of the following challenges hinder cross-sectoral cybersecurity information sharing in your experience? (Select all that apply)

- Lack of trust between sectors
- Legal or regulatory barriers
- Technical incompatibilities
- Insufficient resources
- Other (please specify)

Question 15:

Which informal channels does your organization use for cybersecurity information sharing? (Select all that apply)

- Professional associations
- Industry conferences
- Social media platforms
- Personal networks
- Other (please specify)

Question 16:

On a scale from 1 (Not Important) to 5 (Extremely Important), how important are dual-use cybersecurity technologies to your organization's operations?

Question 17:

How familiar are you with your country's policies and frameworks governing dual-use cybersecurity technologies?

- Not at all familiar
- Slightly familiar
- Moderately familiar
- Very familiar
- Extremely familiar

Question 18:

Which of the following challenges hinder effective regulation and management of dual-use cybersecurity technologies in your experience? (Select all that apply)

- Legal or regulatory barriers
- Ethical considerations
- Technological complexities
- Lack of international cooperation
- Other (please specify)

Question 19:

Are you aware of any cybersecurity technologies with dual-use applications in your country?"

- Yes
- No
- If yes, please provide a brief description (open answer)

Annex 3 – Questions to guide the National Validation Workshops

Question 1:

Considering the preliminary findings on the national cybersecurity landscape, do you agree with the identified strengths and gaps in technology transfer and information sharing mechanisms? What additional factors or perspectives should be considered to provide a more comprehensive understanding?

Purpose:

This prompt fosters interactive discussion among experts, validating the initial findings and uncovering additional insights or overlooked aspects, thereby enhancing the robustness of the case study.

Question 2:

Based on the preliminary findings, do you agree with the assessment of the national cybersecurity strategy's effectiveness and areas for improvement? What additional insights can you provide?

Question 3:

Are there any key stakeholders or collaborative initiatives in the national cybersecurity landscape that have been overlooked in our preliminary analysis?

Question 4:

Do you concur with the identified challenges and gaps in the national cybersecurity framework? Are there additional issues that should be considered?

Question 5:

Are there specific international partnerships or cooperative efforts that have significantly influenced your country's cybersecurity posture? What lessons can be drawn from these experiences?

Question 6:

Do you agree with the defined concept and importance of technology transfer in cybersecurity as presented? Are there additional aspects or perspectives that should be considered?

Question 7:

Are there any legal or regulatory barriers that significantly impact the effectiveness of technology transfer in your country?

Question 8:

Are there any key institutions or collaborative initiatives in the national cybersecurity technology transfer landscape that have been overlooked in our preliminary analysis?

Question 9:

Do you agree with the identified incentives and barriers to cybersecurity technology transfer? Are there additional factors that should be considered?

Question 10:

Based on our findings, are there additional successful cybersecurity technology transfer initiatives that should be highlighted? What lessons can be drawn from these examples?

Question 11:

Are the current national policies and frameworks sufficient to facilitate effective cybersecurity information sharing? What improvements would you suggest?

Question 12:

Are the current threat intelligence sharing mechanisms and tools adequate for your organization's needs? What enhancements would you recommend?

Question 13:

What international best practices in cybersecurity information sharing could be adopted or adapted to improve national mechanisms?

Question 14:

What strategies can be implemented to overcome the identified challenges in cross-sectoral information sharing?

Question 15:

How can informal information-sharing practices be integrated or aligned with formal mechanisms to enhance overall cybersecurity resilience?

Question 16:

Do you agree with the defined concept and importance of dual-use cybersecurity technologies as presented? Are there additional aspects or perspectives that should be considered?

Question 17:

Are the current national policies and frameworks sufficient to manage dual-use cybersecurity technologies effectively? What improvements would you suggest?

Question 18:

What strategies can be implemented to overcome the identified challenges in regulating and managing dual-use cybersecurity technologies?

Question 19:

Based on our findings, are there additional cybersecurity technologies with dual-use applications that should be highlighted? What lessons can be drawn from these examples?

Annex 4 – List of Stakeholders Interviewed

The following organizations took part in interviews (grouped by stakeholder category):

- Government agencies and regulators
 - National Cyber Security Centre
 - Ministry of National Defence
- Private sector representatives (including critical infrastructure operators)
 - Litgrid – Lithuanian electricity transmission system operator
 - Santa Monica Networks
- Research and academic institutions
 - Mykolas Romeris University
 - Kaunas University of Technology
- Civil society or industry associations
 - Lithuanian Riflemen's Union
 - Association of Cyber Security Experts
- Military-related organisations
 - General Jonas Zemaitis Military Academy of Lithuania
 - Cyber defence command of Lithuanian armed forces